

Foraging Behavior and Diet Composition of the Indian False Vampire Bat *Megaderma lyra* (Chiroptera) in Satchori National Park, Habiganj, Bangladesh

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Abstract

Microchiropteran bats play an important ecological role in regulating insect populations, particularly agricultural pests, and contribute to nutrient cycling through the production of guano, which serves as a valuable organic fertilizer and supports diverse microbial communities. However, dietary habits of bats vary depending on species, habitat, season, and prey detection abilities influenced by morphological adaptations. This study investigated the foraging behavior, diet composition, and seasonal variation in the feeding habits of the Indian false vampire bat (*Megaderma lyra*) in Satchori National Park, Habiganj, Bangladesh. Field observations and dietary analyses were conducted from August 2018 to June 2019 in an abandoned house surrounded by palm plantations and forest vegetation. Diet composition was determined through the analysis of prey remains collected from feeding roosts and fecal pellets, while foraging behavior was observed through direct field sightings. The percentage volume and density of dietary components were categorized into four groups: basic food (>20%), constant food (5–20%), supplementary food (1–5%), and chance food (<1%). The bats were primarily active during dusk, with approximately 80% returning to roosts by dawn. Major foraging habitats included tea plantations, paddy fields, and nearby ponds. During the study period, insects belonging to seven orders were identified in the diet. Remains of vertebrates—including fish, frogs, birds, and rodents—were also detected through scales, bones, hair, feathers, and teeth. Among insect prey, Coleopterans constituted the dominant dietary component throughout the study period, while vertebrates and Coleopterans together formed the primary food sources. Hemipterans, Lepidopterans, Orthopterans, and Hymenopterans were classified as constant food items throughout the year, whereas Dipterans and Odonates were recorded as supplementary food sources. These findings highlight the diverse feeding ecology of *Megaderma lyra* and its ecological significance in controlling insect populations and maintaining ecosystem balance in the region.

Keywords: *Megaderma lyra*; Bat ecology; Foraging behavior; Diet composition; Bangladesh; Satchori National Park